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Controllable Synthesis of Carbon Nitride Films with Type-II Heterojunction for Efficient Photoelectrochemical Cells

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ABSTRACT: A simple, straightforward growth method of polymeric carbon nitride (CN) layers on a conductive substrate, with excellent photoelectrochemical activity owing to the formation of a type-II heterojunction by combining two distinct chemical growth methods is reported. The first layer consists of CN prepared from the calcination of a melem–melamine (MeM) adduct; the utilization of MeM enables the preparation of a processable paste which can be easily cast on the conductive substrate. To prepare the second layer, melamine vapor is introduced during calcination. After calcination, two well-connected CN layers with different electronic properties are formed, leading to the formation of a type-II heterojunction. The new CN films exhibit excellent photoelectrochemical properties with a photocurrent density up to 383 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE as well as an acceptable stability over 9 h in 10% (v/v) TEOA-containing 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution, thanks to the enhanced charge separation under illumination. Moreover, the CN films demonstrate good photoelectrochemical activity over a wide pH range, with photocurrent densities of 133, 80, and 118 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ in 0.1 M KOH, 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 , and 0.5 M H_2SO_4 aqueous solutions in the absence of any sacrificial agent, respectively.

1. INTRODUCTION

The water-splitting photoelectrochemical cell (PEC) is being considered as a clean and cost-effective approach to produce hydrogen.^{1–4} In the last years, metal-free polymeric carbon nitride (CN) has emerged as a promising semiconductor material for photoanodes owing to its light-harvesting properties, suitable energy bands positions, stability under a wide pH range, and low price.^{5–12} However, despite the progress both in synthesis and application of CN as a powder,¹³ more controllable synthesis of continuous and uniform CN films, which directly and intimately couple with a conductive substrate is still needed for its realization in PEC cells.^{1,14–16}

To solve these key issues, we and other proposed several physical and chemical deposition methods (e.g., microwave-assisted condensation,¹⁷ physical vapor deposition (PVD),^{18,19} thermal vapor condensation (TVC),^{20–22} chemical vapor deposition (CVD),^{23–25} and liquid-mediated growth approach²⁶). Recently, we proposed a simple and versatile bottom-up approach, based on the doctor-blade technique and a CN precursor paste, for an in situ growth of CN films on various substrates.^{2,6,16,27} Nevertheless, there are still some challenges that hamper their further exploitation such as: (1) the limited amount of suitable CN precursors that afford homogeneous and processable pastes; (2) the fast sublimation of the existing CN precursors during the calcination process, which results in cracks, delamination and even disappearance of the final CN films.^{28–32} Another approach for the in situ growth of CN films is the chemical vapor deposition strategy, which permits the fabrication of thin and compact layers,^{21,33,34} but also suffers to some extent from the limited choice of CN precursors that sublime without degradation.^{2,34,35} One general obstacle for the growth and PEC performance of the CN layer lies in the difficulty in preparing a CN/fluorine-doped tin oxide coated

glass (FTO) substrate interface with intimate contact. Though great efforts have been made on the modification of these CN precursors to give a better intrinsic photoresponse via heteroatom doping,^{36–42} the introduction of foreign functional groups,^{43,44} acid pretreatment^{40,45} and precursor design strategy,^{21,46–48} the weak CN/substrate interface dramatically impedes the charge collection and thus leads to decreased photoresponse.¹ Moreover, the choice of monomers and growth conditions will determine the quality of CN films for PEC application, i.e., defect states can strongly affect charge separation and overall performance.

Melem is an attractive precursor for carbon nitride since it does not easily sublime and is known to afford well-ordered carbon nitride in high yield.⁴⁹ Mixtures of melem and melamine were shown to form denser hydrogen-bonded networks than melem alone;³¹ we hypothesized that such mixtures would combine the favorable properties of melem (low sublimation, high good order, high yield) with the flexibility of supramolecular networks that have been shown to afford processable pastes, which should permit the preparation of homogeneous films with low defect.

Here we show a facile growth of highly photoactive, compact CN layers with altered electronic structure and good adhesion to the FTO substrate. To do so, we employed thermostable melem-melamine (Me-M) adducts^{29,49,50} as precursors for the controllable synthesis of CN films via a doctor-blade technique assisted by a CVD-like process from subliming melamine powder. The in situ growth of the CN film together with the generated type-II heterojunction between two interconnected CN layers greatly facilitates charge separation and migration under illumination, leading to enhanced PEC performance.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials and reagents

Melamine (M, 99%) was bought from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethylene glycol (EG, $\geq 99.5\%$) was supplied by Merck. Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 96%) was supplied by Carlo Erba. Sodium sulphate anhydrous (Na_2SO_4 , AR, 99%) and potassium hydroxide pellets (KOH, AR, 85%) were purchased from Loba Chemie. Triethanolamine (TEOA, $\geq 99.0\%$) was bought from Glentham. All chemicals were used as received without any further pretreatment unless otherwise stated. Additionally, deionized water from a Millipore Direct-Q system (18.2 M Ω cm resistivity) was used for all experiments.

Synthesis of supramolecular precursors

First, melem (Me) was synthesized through the calcination of melamine powder at 400 °C for 12 h in the air using a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. After cooling down to room temperature, bulk melem was ground into a fine light-yellow powder (mortar and pestle) for subsequent use. Afterwards, 3 mmol of melamine and 3 mmol of melem powder were dispersed in 45 mL of DI water by sonication for 15 min. The above mixture was then transferred into a sealed centrifuge tube and shaken for 24 h. The resulting white solid, a supramolecular precursor, was collected by centrifugation and dried under vacuum, and is labelled as MeM. Referring to a previously-reported work by Schnick et al.,³¹ other supramolecular assemblies with different melem/melamine ratios of 3/1 and 1/2 were also synthesized, named as 3MeM and Me2M. In addition, CN films synthesized from melem precursors before (Me(H)) and after self-assembly in water (Me(S)) were also taken into consideration for comparison.

Synthesis of CN1/CN2 hybrid film on FTO

A doctor-blade method was employed to coat the precursor paste onto FTO.²⁷ The purchased FTO (TEC 15A from XOP Glass, Spain) was first cut into rectangular pieces (1.3 cm \times 2.5 cm), cleaned by a successive sonication in an aqueous soap solution, then acetone and ethanol for 30 min each, and finally dried in an air oven at 60 °C before use. For the doctor blade application of the paste, typically, 100 mg of the above-synthesized MeM precursor was ground with 150 μL of EG in an agate mortar to form a homogeneous paste with an appropriate viscosity. A scotch tape (3M company) was employed to shape the profile and simultaneously control the thickness of the precursor film with the help of a glass rod. Then, the tape was removed, and a dry film was obtained by slowly evaporating EG at ~ 85 °C for 30 min on a heating plate. Subsequently, a certain amount of melamine powder was placed at the bottom of a glass tube followed by inserting a piece of FTO-supported precursor film horizontally. The tube was purged with N_2 to replace the air, sealed with Al foil, and finally transferred into a tube furnace. The calcination process was carried out at 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ under N_2 protection (constant 120 mL min⁻¹ flow rate). After cooling down naturally to room temperature, the obtained CN film was labelled as CN-MeM/ M_x , where x stands for the amount of melamine powder (g). When conducting the calcination without melamine powder, i.e., $x = 0$, the resulting CN film was labelled as CN-MeM. For comparison, CN-3MeM/ $M_{0.20}$ and CN-Me2M/ $M_{0.20}$ were also prepared in

the same way by employing 3MeM and Me2M precursors, respectively. CN film by pasting melamine/EG mixture onto FTO was labelled as CN-M. Here for the CN1/CN2 hybrid film, we define layer 1 (CN1) as the CN film synthesized from melem-based precursors, while layer 2 (CN2) as another CN species from melamine powder.

Characterization

The morphologies of the CN films were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-7400F, equipped with a FEG source and operated at an accelerating voltage of 3.5 kV). The crystalline structures of the samples were deduced from X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns, recorded on a Panalytical Empyrean powder diffractometer (equipped with a position sensitive detector X'Celerator) with a scanning time of ~ 7 min for a 2θ range from 5° to 60° using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178$ Å); operation parameters: 40 kV, 30 mA. The chemical states of key elements were determined via X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) on a Thermo Fisher Scientific ESCALAB 250 (K α , 1486.6 eV). Chemical bonding information was also characterized by Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy on a Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS5 with KBr windows and a diamond iD7 ATR optical base. Light absorption and the corresponding band gap of the CN films were measured by UV-vis spectra on a Cary 100 spectrophotometer. Horiba Scientific FluoroMax 4 spectrofluorometer was used for PL measurements at an excitation wavelength of 370 nm. The thickness of CN films was measured by 3D laser confocal scanning microscope (LEXT OLS5000). Solid-state ¹³C CP MAS NMR experiments were carried out on a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz narrow-bore spectrometer, using a 4 mm double-resonance MAS probe at a spinning rate of 8 kHz. ¹³C CP MAS experiments were carried out using a 2.5 μs 1H 90° pulse, 2 ms mixing time and a 3 s recycle delay between acquisitions. The amount of photogenerated H_2 in the reactor headspace was analyzed using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7820 GC system) equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

PEC and electrochemical measurements

Throughout the PEC and electrochemical measurements, a three-electrode system was employed coupled to an Ivium potentiostat (Vertex.1A) with a Pt plate (1.0 cm²), Ag/AgCl (saturated KCl) electrode, and an FTO-supported CN film as the counter, reference, and working electrodes, respectively. The potentials vs. Ag/AgCl were all converted to the values vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) using the Nernst equation at room temperature: $E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{saturated Ag/AgCl}} + 0.0591 \times \text{pH} + 0.197$, unless otherwise stated. Photocurrent measurements were conducted at a bias potential of 1.23 V vs. RHE in a 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution under 1 sun illumination (power density of 100 mW cm⁻²) supplied by the solar simulator (Newport 94011A, built-in air mass AM1.5G filter, and calibrated using a Newport 919P power meter). For comparison, 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 aqueous solution and 0.5 M H_2SO_4 aqueous solution were also used as electrolytes to check the influence of pH on the photocurrent. The open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) was measured under 1 sun illumination. The electrochemically active

surface area (ECSA) of the samples was estimated by cyclic voltammetry between 0 V and 0.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl at different scan rates in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution. Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements were conducted in dark and light from 0 to 1.8 V vs. RHE at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was recorded at applied potentials of 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution. Mott-Schottky measurements were carried out in 1.0 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution on Autolab potentiostat (Metrohm, PGSTAT302N) at 1995.3 Hz and 1000 Hz frequencies. To check the hole extraction efficiency (η), an electrolyte containing 10% (v/v) TEOA and 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution was used. The values were calculated according to the following equation:

$$\eta (\%) = \frac{J_{\text{KOH}}}{J_{\text{TEOA}}} \times 100\%$$

where J_{KOH} and J_{TEOA} are photocurrents obtained in 0.1 M KOH and 0.1 M KOH + 10% (v/v) TEOA electrolytes, respectively.

Incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) values at different wavelengths were calculated through the equation below:

$$\text{IPCE} (\%) = \frac{J (\text{A cm}^{-2}) \times 1240}{\lambda (\text{nm}) \times I (\text{W cm}^{-2})} \times 100\%$$

where J is the photocurrent density, λ is the wavelength (400, 420, 450, and 480 nm) of the incident monochromatic light and I is the light power density. Incident monochromatic light of different wavelengths was obtained by inserting a corresponding band-pass filter (Newport 10BBPF10-400, 10BBPF10-420, 10BBPF10-450, or 10BBPF10-480) between the solar simulator and the PEC cell.

Figure 1. (a,b) SEM images of the MeM adduct at different magnifications; (c) XRD patterns and (d) FTIR spectra of melamine, melem powder, and different supramolecular precursors.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The morphology of melem, which was synthesized through direct calcination of melamine powder at 400 °C (Me(H), "H" stands for after heating), changes from irregular shape to short rod-like structure after reorganization in water (Me(S), "S" stands for reorganization in water, Figure S1 and S2).⁴⁹ We prepared a series of supramolecular assemblies based on melem-melamine in water (referred here as $x\text{Me}y\text{M}$, where $x:y$ is the molar ratio between melem and melamine, which is determined from the reported crystals;^{28,31,51} x and/or y are omitted when equal to 1). 3MeM shows a uniform short rod structure (Figure S3a₁, a₂) while irregular blocks were observed from MeM and Me2M adducts (Figure 1a, b and Figure S3b) probably due to unmatched ratios between the

melem and melamine species in the supramolecular assembly. As shown in Figure 1c, the changes in the diffraction reflection positions from Me(H) to Me(S) confirm the supramolecular assembly formation via H-bonds.⁴⁹ The insertion of melamine molecules into the hexameric rings formed by melem units bridged by H-bonds also leads to a new crystal structure from Me(S) to Me-M adducts.³¹ For higher melamine-to-melem ratios, a superposition of both melamine and Me-M supramolecular diffractions were observed, indicating an excess of melamine (see the illustration of the molecular structure in Figure S1b). Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Figure 1d) shows two sharp peaks of Me(H) above 3300 cm⁻¹, which correspond to N-H vibrations. However, the intensity of these peaks decreases or disappears in the supramolecular assemblies due to the establishment of an

H-bond network.⁵² In addition, the changes in the FTIR spectra between 1480 and 1750 cm^{-1} reflect the differences between the heptazine ring in melem-based species and the triazine ring in the melamine molecule. On account of the similar bonding structures of the building blocks, Me(H), Me(S), and Me-M adducts all exhibit negligible differences in X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements of C1s and N1s (Figure S4). It is worth noting that the melem-based precursors show much better thermal stability than the melamine powder, which was characterized by TGA (precursor powder scratched from the FTO after drying at $\sim 85^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min), which allows the controllable formation of a continuous and uniform CN film (Figure S5). Moreover, only a small weight loss is detected before 100 $^\circ\text{C}$, corresponding to the loss of absorbed or adsorbed water. No signal assigned to ethylene glycol appears, indicating that no carbon impurities exist in the

final CN film. To further confirm the carbon impurities, the elemental analysis and solid-state ^{13}C NMR analysis were performed using CN powder (CN-MP) synthesized from calcination of melamine powder, CN powder (CN-MeM and CN-MeM-M/_{0.20}) obtained by scratching the powder from CN-MeM and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} electrodes. The elemental analysis (Table S1) shows similar C/N molar ratios among these three samples, further indicating no carbon impurities in the CN film. Solid-state ^{13}C cross-polarization magic-angle spinning (CP MAS) NMR spectra showed two distinct signals around ~ 164.1 and ~ 156 ppm for C atoms of CN framework with no other carbon impurities. The first signal was attributed to the carbon atoms ($\text{N}_2\text{-CN}$ or terminal $\text{CN}_2(\text{NH}_x)$), and the second signal was related to the carbon atoms (CN_3), which confirms the presence of tri-s-triazine units in the CN framework (Figure S6).

Figure 2. (a) Schematic illustration of the preparation process of FTO-supported (light-blue) CN film (layer 1 and 2 depicted in orange and yellow, respectively) through a doctor blade technique assisted with vapor deposition from subliming melamine powder; (b,c) Top-view and (d,e) cross-sectional SEM images of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} electrodes on FTO (FTO/CN1/CN2) at different magnifications.

The doctor-blade technique was used to coat precursor pastes onto the FTO substrates as previously reported.²⁷ After calcination at 550 $^\circ\text{C}$ under N_2 atmosphere, flat CN films with strong adhesion to the FTO were obtained (Figure S7). It is worth noting that the shape and area of the paste casting can only be well-maintained for those CN films made from melem-based precursors, unlike what occurs using precursors solely based on melamine (Figure S8). Among the varieties of melem-based precursors investigated in this work, the MeM adduct was chosen for further investigation and PEC measurements because of the high photocurrent density of the resulting CN film, as shown later in this paper (Figure S9). The CN-MeM film (“CN” is added in front of the precursor’s name to represent its corresponding CN film) shows a compact structure (Figure

S10a, b) with a thickness of $\sim 12\ \mu\text{m}$ (Figure S10c). By contrast, CN-M exhibits scattered sheets structure on the FTO due to the fast sublimation of melamine monomer during calcination, resulting in non-continuous film (Figure S11a, b). Further characterization of CN-M electrode can be found in Figure S11c–f. To improve the layer properties, we added a variable amount of melamine powder to the reaction tube (Figure 2a). During the calcination process, melamine sublimation increases the pressure inside the tube, while the MeM layer facilitates the deposition and conversion of the sublimed melamine units to CN. The additional melamine species in the MeM adduct results in abundant small particles on CN rods and a few large sheets on the surface — forming another CN layer (CN2, Figure 2b). The underlying layer (CN1), i.e. the CN film obtained

from the MeM adduct phase, is consistent with the original MeM precursor in shape, but with additional adsorbed small particles (Figure 2b–d). The thickness of CN1 layer was measured as 20 μm , while only a rough estimate of 10 μm can be made for CN2 on account of the unevenness of the CN1 surface at a microscopic scale, which inhibits the formation of fully uniform film. The cross-sectional SEM

image reveals a tight CN film, which is strongly attached to the FTO substrate (Figure 2e). Moreover, the comparison of the morphologies of CN-Me2M/ $M_{0.20}$ and CN-3MeM/ $M_{0.20}$ (CN-precursor name/ M_x , where x (g) represents the mass of the melamine powder added to the tube for vapor deposition), shows that the surface of the CN film is more compact at higher M/Me ratio (Figure S12).

Figure 3. (a) XRD patterns and (b) UV-vis spectra of CN-MeM/ M_x films on FTO prepared with variable added melamine powder, the inset in (b) shows the Tauc plots of CN-MeM and CN-MeM/ $M_{0.20}$; (c) Global and partially zoomed-in (3450–2750 cm^{-1}) FTIR spectra of MeM/ M samples; (d) C 1s and (e) N 1s XPS spectra of CN-MeM, CN-MeM/ $M_{0.05}$, CN-MeM/ $M_{0.20}$, and CN-MeM/ $M_{0.80}$.

As shown in Figure 3a, except for the diffraction peaks of the FTO substrate, the XRD pattern of CN-MeM/ M_x shows two typical peaks of CN materials at 2θ of 12.8° and 27.6° , corresponding to (100) and (002) planes.⁵³ Moreover, the increasing intensity of the (002) peak at higher amounts of melamine powder reflects the increase in the CN layer's thickness along with an improved interlayer stacking. The UV-vis spectra of all CN-MeM/ M_x films disclose that the smallest band gap of 2.47 eV is for the CN-MeM with only one layer (Figure 3b). The heterojunction between CN1 and CN2 only exists at the interface between the materials. The introduction of melamine vapor results in an apparent blue-shift of the total absorption features, with a larger band gap ranging from 2.54 to 2.69 eV (Figure S13), owing to the typical absorption of CN, which is synthesized from melamine (Figure S11d). Specifically, the bandgaps of CN-M, CN-MeM, and CN-MeM/ $M_{0.20}$ are 2.75, 2.47, and 2.65 eV, respectively. The FTIR spectra of the CN-MeM/ M_x films show a series of peaks in the region between 1700 and 1100 cm^{-1} , which correspond to the typical stretching modes of C–N heterocycles (Figure 3c). The peak at 805 cm^{-1} is attributed to the breathing vibration of the heptazine units in CN films. Broad peaks between 3450 and 2750 cm^{-1} are

ascribed to the stretching vibration of N–H in amino groups due to incomplete polymerization. The weaker absorption in the N–H stretching region, as displayed in the partially zoomed-in FTIR spectra, suggests that CN-MeM contains fewer defects than CN-M.⁴⁹ All the high-resolution C 1s XPS spectra of the CN-MeM/ M_x samples (Figure 3d) can be well fitted using two peaks centered at 288.1 eV and 284.8 eV, which are assigned to C=N–C in heptazine units in the CN framework and sp^2 hybridized C=C from the carbonaceous environment.²⁷ The N 1s XPS spectra reveal three peaks centered at 398.6, 399.6, and 400.8 eV, corresponding to N species in the forms of C=N–C, N–(C)₃, and N–H, respectively (Figure 3e).⁵⁴

PEC performance was evaluated in a three-electrode system using 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution as the electrolyte under one sun illumination. The photocurrent densities vs. time were measured for all CN films at an applied potential of 1.23 V vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) using back-side illumination unless stated otherwise. A CN-MeM film exhibits a photocurrent density of 50 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ (Figure S9a), which is higher than that of the films synthesized from Me(H) and Me(S) precursors. The vapor deposition of a second CN layer from melamine powder leads to higher

photocurrent densities than the initial ones owing to the formation of a heterojunction (Figure S9b). Optimizing the Me/M molar ratio and the amount of added melamine powder leads to the photoanode — FTO coated with a photoactive CN-MeM/M_{0.20} heterojunction — with the highest photocurrent density, i.e., 133 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ (Figure S9b, Figure S14 and S15). The negligible initial decay of the photocurrent density at ‘light on’ is suggestive of a low rate of photogenerated electron-hole pair recombination, while the fast photocurrent decay when the light is turned off is indicative of a low number of trapped charges.¹⁶ It is worth noting that this photocurrent value is among the best

reported for CN films (Table S2). To highlight the advantage of such in situ approach for CN film growth, photocurrent densities of different CN films were also measured by pasting the corresponding powders onto an FTO substrate. In the latter cases, significantly lower values were measured, presumably due to low adhesion of the CN film to the FTO substrate (Figure S16a). Moreover, when depositing CoO(OH)_x cocatalyst on the CN film, it cannot permeate deeply into the CN1 layer to form a homogeneous deposition. Therefore, no photocurrent enhancement occurs relative to the CN-MeM/M_{0.20} electrode (Figure S16b).

Figure 4. (a) Photocurrent densities of CN-M, CN-MeM and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} films on FTO at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 10% (v/v) TEOA-containing 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution under one sun illumination; (b) Histogram of H₂ production of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} as a function of time in 10% TEOA (v/v) in 0.1 M KOH (blue color) and an aqueous solution containing 0.25 M Na₂S and 0.35 M Na₂SO₃ (pH 12.86) (dark yellow color); (c) Double-layer capacitance values of CN-MeM/M_x films; (d) LSV curves of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution in the dark and under one sun illumination, respectively; (e) Photocurrent density (1.23 V vs. RHE) of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solutions under one sun back-side illumination; (f) Proposed water splitting PEC operation scheme with a type-II heterojunction in a photoactive CN-MeM/M_{0.20} film over FTO (FTO/CN2/CN1) serving as the photoanode, without a hole scavenger.

The photocurrent density of the CN-MeM/M_{0.20} film upon front-side illumination was of similar value (106 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$), implying an efficient diffusion of electrons from the CN layer to the conductive substrate. The ratio of the front/back photocurrent densities is *ca.* 80%, suggesting an efficient electron transfer from the upper CN film surface to the FTO substrate (Figure S17). The incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} film is 5.2% at 400 nm with a photocurrent onset at \sim 450 nm (Figure S18a), while the IPCE values of CN-M and CN-MeM are 1.8% and 2.2% (Figure S18b). This results indicate better charge separation in CN-MeM/M_{0.20} with a double layered structure. EIS presents a smaller semicircle and lower interfacial charge transfer resistance for CN-MeM/M_{0.20} (Figure S19), compared to those of CN-M and CN-MeM. In addition, further increase of the first CN layer’s thickness resulted in a decay of the measured photocurrent densities, yet the values remained above 80 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ (Figure S20).

The photocurrent densities of CN-M, CN-MeM, and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} were measured at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution in the presence of a hole scavenger, triethanolamine (TEOA), with enhanced values up to 120, 177, and 383 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, respectively (Figure 4a). These measurements indicate that the charge-transfer bottleneck in this system lies in the difficulty of hole extraction. Compared with the photocurrent densities measured in KOH electrolyte only, the calculated charge transfer efficiencies (E_{ct}) are 31.7%, 28.2%, and 34.7% for CN-M, CN-MeM/M_{0.20}, and CN-MeM, respectively, an indication of the good charge separation in the CN-MeM/M_{0.20} film (Figure S21a-c), which is further evidenced by PL characterization (Figure S21d). CN-MeM/M_{0.20} exhibits low PL intensity compared to that of CN-M and CN-MeM, suggesting that the photo-excited charge carriers were more easily separated and transferred due to a type II heterojunction. In the presence of TEOA, the CN-MeM/M_{0.20} film demonstrates

acceptable stability over 9 h (Figure S22). In addition, the H₂ generation in the presence of 10% (v/v) TEOA in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution, and an aqueous solution containing 0.25 M Na₂S and 0.35 M Na₂SO₃ (pH 12.86) was tracked by gas chromatography (GC), and showed Faradaic efficiencies up to 76.23% and 94.81%, respectively (Figure 4b, Figure S23). Here the H₂ is evaluated from Pt counter electrode.⁵⁵

Electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) measurements reveal a good correlation between the double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) and the photocurrent density of the CN-MeM/M_x films (Figure 4c and Figure S24a). However, the additional second layer causes a small decrease in the ECSA, further indicating the more compact nature of the CN layer from melamine powder. Nevertheless, the quality of the two layers together with the electronic heterojunction between two individual CN layers in CN-MeM/M_{0.20} (Figure S24b) result in better charge separation and higher PEC performance. The good charge separation is also evident from the high open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 0.571 V for the CN-MeM/M_{0.20} compared to that of the other films (Figure S25).

Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} (Figure 4d) disclose a very low onset potential of 0.147 V vs. RHE. Compared with the unnoticeable change of the current density in the dark before ~1.7 V, the linear increase of the photocurrent under illumination demonstrates a typical PEC behavior. The increase in current above ~1.7 V is due to the electrocatalytic reaction. This low overpotential value further corroborates a good charge separation under illumination. Additional measurements of the LSV curves of CN-MeM and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} upon on/off cycling under the same conditions can be found in Figure S26. Photocurrent measurements of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} were also conducted at neutral and acidic environments using 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ and 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous solutions as electrolytes (Figure 4e). The CN-MeM/M_{0.20} film exhibits an excellent photoresponse over the whole pH range. In H₂SO₄ electrolyte, an outstanding value of 118 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ is observed, which is higher than those of the recently reported works (Table S2); the related V_{oc} value is 0.291 V (Figure S27) and the IPCE is 4.2% at 400 nm (Figure S18a). By contrast, CN-MeM shows much lower photocurrent densities of <40 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ in both H₂SO₄ and Na₂SO₄ electrolytes (Figure S28).

The energy band diagram was calculated using Mott-Schottky measurements (Figure S29) and Tauc plot analysis of the optical absorption spectra (Figure 3b, Figure S11d, and S13). CN-MeM (CN1) and CN-M (CN2) form a type II heterojunction (Figure 4f). Under illumination, photoexcited electrons migrate from the CB of CN2 to that of CN1 and then migrate and collected at the FTO, whereas the holes move in the opposite direction. The band edge potentials facilitate charge separation, which decreases the recombination rate, thus leading to enhanced PEC performance.^{35,56,57}

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we demonstrated a facile synthesis of highly efficient polymeric carbon nitride layers as photoanodes in PEC by combining two distinct chemical growth methods. For the first layer, we casted a new

monomer, which is based on a melem-melamine supramolecular assembly, using a doctor blade technique on an FTO substrate. The excellent processability and thermal stability of MeM allow the fabrication of controllable, continuous, and uniform CN films with relatively low defect concentration and strongly connected to the FTO substrate. The additional vapor deposition, which occurs during the synthesis from the added melamine powder enables the formation of a second compact layer with dissimilar electronic band positions on top of the first CN layer. The two connected CN layers create an electronic heterojunction, which greatly facilitates the charge separation processes under illumination. As a result, the optimized hybrid CN film gives an impressive photocurrent density up to 133 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE, a large V_{oc} of 0.571 V, as well as a very low onset potential of 0.147 V under one sun illumination without any sacrificial agent in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution, and 383 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ and acceptable stability over 9 h in 10% (v/v) TEOA-containing 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution. Moreover, it is performing over the whole pH scale with photocurrent densities of 80 and 118 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ in 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ and 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous solutions, respectively. We demonstrated that the combination of several growth methods permits overcoming the drawbacks and exploiting the benefits of each method. Together with the introduction of new melem-based monomers, we foresee that it will develop the full potential of all developed techniques and lead to a range of high-performance CN-based materials in the photo(electro)catalysis and other electronic applications.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at XXXXXX

Additional supramolecular assemblies, precursors, or films characterization (SEM, XPS, TGA, solid-state NMR, optical), electrochemical measurements, GC, and PEC performance, comparison tables.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Supporting Information

Controllable Synthesis of Carbon Nitride Film with Type-II Heterojunction for Efficient Photoelectrochemical Cells

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Figure S1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication of (a) Me(S) and (b) 3MeM adduct phase; (c) Corresponding H-bonding models.

Figure S2. SEM images of (a₁, a₂) melem powder synthesized by direct calcination of melamine at 400 °C for 12 h in the air and (b₁, b₂) supramolecular melem, after self-assembly in water.

As illustrated in **Figure S1a**, by calcinating melamine directly at 400 °C for 12 h under the protection of inert N₂ atmosphere, large and irregular melem (Me(H)) structures were obtained (**Figure S2a₁, a₂**). Dispersing this melem species in water by sonication and subsequent shaking overnight resulted in the organization of the melem molecules into a supramolecular assembly with short rod-like morphology and an average length of several micrometers (**Figure S2b₁, b₂**).

Figure S3. SEM images of (a₁, a₂) 3MeM and (b₁, b₂) Me2M supramolecular precursors.

Figure S4. (a) C 1s XPS and (b) N 1s XPS spectra of melam-based supramolecular precursors.

All C 1s XPS spectra show similar shape with a fitting peak at 288.1 eV, assigned to the sp^2 C in triazine or heptazine units, and two extra peaks centered at 284.8 and 286.3 eV coming from the carbonaceous environment.¹ All N 1s XPS spectra were deconvoluted into three peaks at 398.6, 399.6, and 400.8 eV, which are ascribed to C=N-C, N-(C)₃, and N-H, respectively.

Figure S5. TGA analysis of melamine, M(H), and MeM supramolecular assemblies.

Figure S6. Solid-state ¹³C CP MAS NMR spectra of CN (spinning side bands are marked using *).

Figure S7. Strong coupling of CN film of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} is verified by (a) scotch-tape test followed by (b) finger test.

Figure S8. Digital photos of MeM, Me(H), Me(S), and melamine precursors on FTO-coated glass substrates and the corresponding CN films formed after calcination. Here CN-M① and CN-M② are CN films synthesized in different batches from a melamine paste.

Figure S9. (a) Photocurrent density (at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution) of CN films obtained by calcination of Me-based precursors at 550 °C for 4 h under N₂ atmosphere (a) without and (b) with the help of melamine powder.

Figure S10. SEM images of FTO-supported CN film synthesized from MeM supramolecular assembly. (a, b) top-view, (c) cross-section.

Figure S11. (a) Top-view, (b) cross sectional SEM images and (c) XRD pattern of carbon nitride electrode synthesized from melamine (CN-M); (d) UV-vis spectra and Tauc plots (inset) of carbon nitride powder scraped off from CN-M electrode. Extrapolation of the linear part (using the Tauc plot method) indicates the direct (optical) band gap of carbon nitride to be 2.75 eV. (e) C 1s XPS and (f) N 1s XPS spectra of carbon nitride powder scraped off from CN-M electrode.

Figure S12. (a, b) SEM images of (a₁, a₂) CN-Me₂M/M_{0.20} and (b₁, b₂) CN-3MeM/M_{0.20}.

Figure S13. Tauc plots of (a) CN-MeM/M_{0.05}, (b) CN-MeM/M_{0.10}, (c) CN-MeM/M_{0.40}, and (d) CN-MeM/M_{0.80}. Extrapolation of the linear part indicates the direct (optical) band gap determined using the Tauc plot method to be: (a) 2.54 eV, (b) 2.56 eV, (c) 2.67 eV, (d) 2.69 eV.

Figure S14. Photocurrent densities of CN-MeM/ M_x films on FTO prepared with different amounts of melamine powder at a potential of 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution under one sun illumination.

Figure S15. Relationship between the melamine mass added to the tube during calcination and the photocurrent density (at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution) of the final CN film obtained by thermal polymerization of MeM precursor at 550 °C for 4 h under N_2 atmosphere.

Figure S16. (a) Photocurrent density of FTO substrate and different CN films by pasting corresponding powder onto FTO under one sun illumination from the back side; (b) Photocurrent density of CN-MeM/ $M_{0.20}$ photoelectrode after depositing $\text{CoO}(\text{OH})_x$ nanoparticles by a two-step impregnation process: First, the electrode is immersed into an aqueous solution of cobalt nitrate (0.1 M) for 10 min and dried in air. Subsequently, the electrode is quickly dipped into aqueous ammonia solution (25% wt.) and dried again.

Figure S17. Photocurrent density of CN-MeM/ $M_{0.20}$ obtained under one sun illumination from the front- and back-side.

Figure S18. Incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} in 0.1 M KOH (blue, circle) and 0.5 M H₂SO₄ (black, square) aqueous solutions, respectively; (b) IPCE of CN-M (green, circle) and CN-MeM (red, circle) in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution.

Figure S19. Nyquist plots of CN-M, CN-MeM, and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} at applied potentials of 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution. The inset shows the equivalent circuit for the fitting of Nyquist plots.

Figure S20. (a) Photocurrent densities of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} films with different MeM layer amounts (1, 2, 3, and 4 layers) on FTO at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution under one sun illumination; (b) Photocurrent densities (left scale, red circles) and film thicknesses (right scale, blue squares) changing with increasing MeM adduct layers.

Figure S21. Photocurrent density comparison (at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 10% (v/v) TEOA-containing 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution, and 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution) of CN-M, CN-MeM, and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} under one sun back-side illumination; (d) Photoluminescence (PL) spectra of CN-M, CN-MeM, and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} under excitation at 370 nm.

Figure S22. Durability measurement of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} in 10% (v/v) TEOA-containing 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution at 1.23 V vs. RHE under one sun illumination from the back-side.

Figure S23. GC of H₂ production using CN photoanodes as a function of time in 10% TEOA (v/v) in (a) 0.1 M KOH (blue color) and (b) an aqueous solution containing 0.25 M Na₂S and 0.35 M Na₂SO₃ (pH 12.86).

Figure S24. Plots of cathodic and anodic current densities of (a) CN-MeM/M_x samples with different amounts of melamine powder, (b) CN-MeM and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} at $-0.1 \text{ V vs. Ag/AgCl}$ changing with potential scan rates.

Figure S25. Open-circuit potential of (a) CN-MeM, (b) CN-MeM/M_{0.20}, (c) CN-Me2M/M_{0.20}, and (d) CN-3MeM/M_{0.20} electrodes in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution.

Amongst the four CN films (CN-MeM, CN-MeM/M_{0.20}, CN-Me2M/M_{0.20}, and CN-3MeM/M_{0.20}) with different components investigated, the highest open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 0.571 V for CN-MeM/M_{0.20} reflects the most efficient charge separation of photogenerated electrons and holes, which largely stems from the formed heterojunction between interconnected CN layers and the proper molar ratio of each monomer in the Me-M adduct that can effectively result in such a unique structure.

Figure S26. LSV curves of CN-MeM and CN-MeM/M_{0.20} in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution upon on/off cycling with interval time 5 s at scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹ under one sun illumination.

Figure S27. Open-circuit potential of CN-MeM/M_{0.20} electrode in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous solution.

Figure S28. Photocurrent density (at 1.23 V vs. RHE) of CN-MeM with back-side illumination in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solutions under one sun illumination.

Figure S29. Mott-Schottky plots of (a) CN-MeM, (b) CN-M, and (c) CN-MeM/M_{0.20} and bare FTO electrodes; (d) The corresponding energy band diagram.

Table S1 Elemental analysis data of carbon nitrides (atomic percentage)

Sample name	Carbon (at. %)	Nitrogen (at. %)	Hydrogen (at. %)	C/N
Melamine	19.97	40.13	39.91	0.498
MeM	24.34	42.14	33.52	0.578
CN-MP	32.8	49.33	17.88	0.665
CN-MeM	32.86	49.14	18	0.669
CN-MeM/M _{0.20}	32.56	48.93	18.51	0.666

Table S2 Summary of PEC performance of CN materials (All substrates are FTO unless otherwise stated)

Photoanode CN-based material	Raw materials	Methods	Photocurrent ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$)	Potential (V) vs. RHE	Onset potential (V) vs. RHE	Electrolyte	Light intensity	Ref.
In situ grown double-layered CN film (CN-MeM/M _{0.20})	Melamine	Doctor-blade technique assisted with CVD-like process	133	1.23	0.243	0.1 M KOH	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	This work
			383	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
			80	1.23	N/A	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
			118	1.23	N/A	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
Porous crystalline CN film	Melamine	Seeded crystallization of CN monomers followed by calcination at high temperature	116	1.23	0.25	0.1 M KOH	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	2
			245	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
Compact carbon nitride polymer	Melamine, cyanuric chloride	Evaporation polymerization method	~150	1.23	N/A	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	3
	Melamine							
	Cyanuric chloride							
In situ grown porous CN/rGO film	Melamine, graphene oxide	Doctor-blade technique	124.5	1.23	0.3	0.1 M KOH	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	4
			272	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
Carbon nitride/reduced graphene oxide film	Melamine, cyanuric acid, graphene oxide	Doctor-blade technique	72	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	5
			660	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
			30	1.23	N/A	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
			45	1.23	N/A	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	
Ni Embedded CN _x Films	Cyanuric acid, 2,4-diamino-6-phenyl-1,3,5-triazine, nickel chloride	liquid-mediated pathway, evaporation polymerization method (in situ vapor condensation)	69.8	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	6

S-doped thin films of phenyl-modified CN	Cyanuric acid, 2,4-diamino-6-phenyl-1,3,5-triazine	Liquid-mediated approach, in situ vapor condensation	60	1.23	N/A	0.1 M KOH	50 W white LED ($\lambda > 410$ nm, HLN-60H-24A, Mean Well)	7
PCN film	Melamine, trithiocyanuric acid	Molten mediate polymerization, FTO glass was buried into the powder	100	1.23	N/A	1.0 M KOH	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	8
g-CN films	Dicyandiamide	Molten mediate polymerization	63	1.23	N/A	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	9
g-CN400	Melamine	In situ vapor condensation	75	1.23	N/A	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5	10
CN	Cyanamide	anodic aluminum oxide membrane assisted growth	30.2	1.23	N/A	0.2 M Na ₂ SO ₄	500 W Xe lamp	11
CNBC-U/TiO ₂	Cyanuric chloride, cyanuric acid	Solvothermal method with post-annealing	32	1.23	~0.32	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	Solar light (1 sun, AM 1.5)	12
CNBC			2		N/A			

Supporting Information References

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